

Investigating Linear Solvers for Power Grid Analysis with Exascale Computing: A Journey of Learning and Collaboration

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Abstract—The focus of this work is direct sparse linear solvers using High-Performance Computing (HPC) for large-scale power systems resembling power grids in the United States. It explores supercomputers at Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility, Summit and Frontier, for comparing both performance and optimization strategies. MA57 and Amesos2 solvers offer versatile solutions for traditional CPU-based computations. On the other hand, cuSolver and rocSolver tap into the power of GPU computing for accelerated performance. The challenges of power flow analysis are addressed by the implementation of LU-decomposition algorithms with varied optimization techniques and by evaluating accuracy and stability through residual analysis. Beyond technical gains, this work underscores the significance of collaboration and diverse expertise in HPC for innovative analysis of power grid systems. Such analysis is critical for resilient infrastructure against burgeoning threats like climate change and cyberattacks.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study involves exploring HPC environments to evaluate the performance of linear solvers using supercomputers, Summit and Frontier, at the Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility. The Summit system hosts a total of 4,608 compute nodes. Each node has two 21-core IBM Power9 CPUs and six NVIDIA V100 GPUs [1]. An exemplar of exascale capabilities, the Frontier system houses a total of 9,408 AMD compute nodes. Each node has one 64-core 3rd Gen AMD EPYC CPU and four Purpose Built AMD Instinct 250X Graphics Compute Dies (GCD), where one GCD consists of two GPUs [2]. This comparison serves as a cornerstone for understanding performance disparities and optimization strategies on different hardware architectures. The focus is on direct sparse linear solvers to evaluate large-scale, synthetic linear systems representing Texas, Western, and Eastern power grids in the United States (US). Analyzing AC optimal power flow problems holds importance in discerning the vulnerabilities within the US power grid in the face of multifaceted risks stemming from climate change, environmental disasters, erosion, cybersecurity, physical attacks, and renewable resources [3]. The structure of a power grid system is characterized by a sparse, indefinite matrix that demands the utilization of various factorization algorithms for effective solving. The project encompasses testing Trilinos Amesos2 CPU-based solvers, KLU2 and ShyLUBasker, and examining GPU-based solvers, NVIDIA cuSolver versus AMD rocSolver on distinct architecture configurations. The MA57 solver serves as a baseline for these comparisons. Direct sparse solvers are designed to take advantage of sparsity patterns that arise in real-world problems, leading to memory and computational efficiency.

2. DIRECT SPARSE LINEAR SOLVERS

Sparse linear solvers can handle a range of characteristics, including ill-conditioned, symmetric, or indefinite matrices [4]. LU-decomposition algorithms profit from optimization techniques like iterative refinement (IR), refactorization methods, exploiting matrix symmetry, and GPU acceleration. Solvers capabilities in this study are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Comparative Overview of Sparse Linear Solvers

Solver	MA57	KLU2	ShyLU Basker	cuSolver KLU-RF	rocSolver KLU-RF
Exploit symmetry	Yes	No	No	No	No
Primary algorithm	LDL^T	LU	LU	LU refactor	LU refactor
Follows w/ IR	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Norm equation	∞ -norm	2-norm	2-norm	∞ -norm	∞ -norm
GPU accel.	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Open source	No	Yes	Yes	No	No

2.1 Sparse Linear Equations and Solver Strategies

The system of linear equations is represented as $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$, where \mathbf{A} is a symmetric, indefinite $n \times n$ sparse matrix, \mathbf{b} is an $n \times 1$ right-hand-side (RHS) vector, and \mathbf{x} is the $n \times 1$ solution vector [5]. Directly computing the solution vector $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{b}$ is too computationally expensive for such large-scale systems. As a result, matrix \mathbf{A} is factorized into a lower triangular matrix \mathbf{L} and an upper triangular matrix \mathbf{U} such that, $(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{LU}$, where \mathbf{P} represents a permutation matrix that transforms rows or columns of \mathbf{A} to reduce the number of nonzeros factors [6]. Since $(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{Ax} \equiv \mathbf{LUx}$ the system of equations is formulated as, $\mathbf{LUx} = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{P})^{-1}$. Components of the RHS vector \mathbf{b} are reordered by multiplication with the permutation matrix \mathbf{P} . Let $\mathbf{z} := \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{P})^{-1}$ and obtain the solution vector by a series of substitutions. Forward substitution gives, $\mathbf{Ly} = \mathbf{z}$, and solving $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{z}$, where \mathbf{y} is a partial solution. Backward substitution gives, $\mathbf{Ux} = \mathbf{y}$, and solving $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{y}$ for the solution vector. When the matrix exhibits symmetry optimization opportunities arise. In this case, \mathbf{A} is factorized into a lower triangular \mathbf{L} , a 1×1 or 2×2 diagonal block \mathbf{D} , and the transpose of \mathbf{L} , \mathbf{L}^T . The symmetric system is formulated as $\mathbf{LDL}^T\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{P})^{-1}$. Only the lower triangular matrix \mathbf{L} is needed for efficient solving as shown in the back substitution step, $\mathbf{DL}^T\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{y}$, where $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{DL}^T)^{-1}\mathbf{y}$, which gives $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{Ly}$.

2.2 Residual Analysis and Accuracy Assessment

To assess solver accuracy, the residual vector \mathbf{r} is obtained as $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{Ax}$. The norm of the residual $\|\mathbf{r}\|$ and the norm of the solution vector $\|\mathbf{b}\|$ are calculated to obtain the relative residual, $\|\mathbf{r}\|/\|\mathbf{b}\|$. This ratio offers insights into solution convergence and accuracy [7]. A smaller relative residual indicates higher accuracy and increased stability of the solver. In cases of ill-conditioned matrices, discrepancies and outliers in relative residuals are expected and may reveal error patterns that provide new directions for unique problem-solving.

3. TEST CASES

The test cases under investigation are synthetic linear systems extracted from AC optimal power flow analysis for Texas, Western US, and Eastern US power grids [8]. The model specifications for the Eastern US grid are detailed in Table 2. Each test case contains a set of systems with symmetric, sparse matrices and corresponding RHS vectors. The data set reveals the size of each matrix and the number of non-zero entries (NNZ) [9]. Unpacking the non-zero entries (NNZun) fully expands the matrix with all explicit non-zero entries, including those not stored in the file [10]. This storage optimization becomes critical as some solvers, such as MA57, require only the lower triangular of the matrix [11], while others like KLU, require a fully expanded matrix. Each grid has an archetype number of buses within its corresponding power grid system. Buses serve as junction points within an electrical network and play a pivotal role in facilitating the connection of electrical elements and the distribution of power across local lines [4].

TABLE 2. Power Grid Model Specifications

Grid Model	Bus Size	Matrix Size	NNZ	NNZun	No. sets
Eastern US	70,000	1.6m \times 1.6m	4.9m	8.3m	17

4. RESULTS

The experiments reveal performance analysis and convergence behavior of the Eastern US power grid systems on different hardware architectures. This test case was verified a minimum of 3 times for reproducibility. Figures 1 and 2 depict the computation time and relative residuals of the Eastern US (70k-bus) grid model respectively. Similar results were found for the Texas and Western US grid analysis, which are not shown in this condensed paper. MA57, the gold-standard solver, performs significantly faster on Frontier than on Summit. KLU2 has the slowest performance of all solvers but maintains a notable degree of stability. ShyLUBasker on Summit and Frontier performs closely to MA57 on Summit. While rocSolver KLU-RF performs closely to MA57 on Frontier. Most notably, cuSolver KLU-RF has the fastest performance of all solvers with the one-time CPU cost at index 0-2 before GPU utilization, highlighting a promising future GPU-based solvers. Typically, a relative residual ≥ 1.0 is considered poor solver stability as illustrated for ShyLUBasker and rocSolver KLU-RF on Frontier. Ideally, values $\leq 10^{-7}$ substantiate optimal accuracy and stability. ShyLUBasker on Summit revealed improved accuracy despite slower runtimes when compared to Frontier. This discrepancy demonstrates a

trade-off occurring in runtime performance versus solver stability. The solution for rocSolver KLU-RF failed to converge at index 16 and is omitted. cuSolver KLU-RF maintains adequate stability throughout with the exception of index 16. MA57 provides the strongest accuracy and stability of all solvers in this study, maintaining its gold-standard status.

Fig. 1. Total runtimes for the Eastern US (70k-bus) test cases reveal solver performance discrepancies.

Fig. 2. Relative residual analysis for the Eastern US (70k-bus) test cases show fluctuations in stability and accuracy.

5. CONCLUSION

The results detail the intricacies of solver performance, underscoring the impact of symmetry, optimization techniques, and accuracy evaluation for analyzing large-scale power flow problems. Exploiting GPU parallelization proves to be an encouraging prospect for numerical linear systems. Continued research will improve the efficiency and accuracy of analyzing these increasingly complex power grid systems. The grid faces risks from climate change, environmental disasters, erosion, cybersecurity breaches, physical attacks, and more [12]. The power of collaboration in High-Performance Computing has the potential to guide infrastructure policy that ensures the US sustains a resilient power grid that meets the unique needs of each State and is protected against any potential threats. The unification of diverse perspectives in HPC is a necessity to effectively address such challenges at the forefront of technology.

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